

Tracking soil health in response to soil tillage

Problem

Soils are vital substrates for growing crops, but soil compaction and organic carbon loss threaten soil health and agricultural productivity. Ploughing of arable soils disrupts soil structure, making soils more vulnerable to erosion and organic matter loss. A variety of practices can be applied to minimise soil disturbance. Methods are needed to help land managers track soil health in response to a change in soil management practice.

Solution

Two indicators of soil characteristics and function were assessed in winter grain crops drilled directly into uncultivated soil compared with ploughed soil: 1) Soil aggregate stability as an indicator of soil physical structure; and 2) Soil organic matter content as an indicator of soil moisture retention and carbon storage.

Benefits

Changes in soil health occur over a period of several years following a shift in soil management. Indicators of soil health allow these changes to be tracked through time and assessed in relation to other agronomic factors (such as weed control), yield and economic returns to the farm business.

Applicability box

Theme

Soil management
Soil health indicators

Keywords

Soil cultivation
Soil structure
Soil carbon

Context

Scotland

Application time

Autumn (pre-sowing) to summer (harvest and post-harvest)

Required time

An annual crop growing season

Period of impact

Between 1-5 years of annual growing cycles

Equipment

Spade or auger, sample bags

Best in

Arable cropping

Practical recommendation

- Soil should be sampled by taking several soil samples to a defined depth in a sampling design that covers different areas across the field (e.g., AHDB recommends walking a 'W' pattern across the sampling area, stopping at least 25 times to sample).
- Soil health indicators could vary with soil depth. The amount of carbon held in the soil is highest in the top 10 cm and will decrease with depth. The presence of compaction can affect soil structure in different parts of the soil profile.
- Samples can be collected pre-sowing, during crop growth and after harvest. It is important to take samples at the same time of year in each year of sampling, as soil indicators can vary within the season.
- Soil can be sampled by digging a soil pit (e.g. 20 x 20 x 20 cm) or using an auger to remove a soil column of known volume

Soil core sampled with an auger (Kieran Walter)

(**Figure 1**). Excavated soil (0.5 Kg) is transferred into a bag and refrigerated prior to sending away for analysis.

- A bulk density estimate is required to calculate soil organic carbon stocks in tonnes per hectare. Bulk density is the dry mass of a known volume of soil and can be carried out by a soil analytical lab. The soil sample is weighed, then dried and re-weighed.
- Soil organic carbon can be measured by analytical labs directly by Dumas combustion or wet acidified dichromate oxidation or indirectly by loss on ignition (LOI) of organic matter, although estimating soil carbon from LOI is potentially inaccurate and prone to errors. For carbonate-rich soils (e.g., Machair soils), additional steps are needed using the first two techniques to quantify the contribution from inorganic carbon (carbonates).
- Soil tests for carbon usually report carbon as a % of the soil dry mass. The amount of organic carbon to a 10 cm depth in soil with a carbon content of 1% and a bulk density of 1.3 g dry mass/cm³ is: 1.0 x 1.3 x 10 = 13 tonnes/ha of carbon.
- Water-stable aggregate stability is tested by air-drying the soil, then sieving soil through 8 mm and 2 mm sieves, retaining the aggregates that are larger than 2 mm. The soil aggregates (2-8 mm) are subjected to water stability analysis using the wet-sieving method. Water-stable aggregate stability is calculated as a % of total soil weight (i.e. 100*(mass of stable aggregates/(mass of stable+unstable aggregates))).
- A positive relation between soil %organic matter and %water-stable aggregates has been demonstrated (**Figure 2**) and relates to the binding potential of organic components (plant residues, plant or microbial exudates, fungal hyphae, humic material).

Figure 2. Soils sampled from fields of direct drilled winter grain crops (pale coloured circles) generally showed higher soil aggregate stability and higher organic matter content (Loss On Ignition) compared with crops grown on ploughed soils (dark coloured circles).

Further information

Further reading

Karley AJ, Banks G, Brandt J, Swyst I, Mitchell C, Hawes C, Boldrin D, Loades K, Ndlovu T, Zuta A, Begg G. 2025. Impact of zero tillage winter grain crops on soil health indicators. Summary report of farm trials in 2024 for the RESAS project B3-1 Co-designing and implementing best-fit farming practices. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15728881

Weblinks

Check these resources for more practical recommendations.

<https://ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/action-plan-for-soil-testing>

<https://ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/how-to-collect-a-soil-sample>

About this practice abstract

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